

ASSESSING PRIMARY LEVEL LEARNERS: STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE KNOWLEDGE TESTING

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Abstract:

This article is devoted to modern methods of assessing knowledge primary school students and delves into the theme of assessing primary level learners and explores strategies for effective knowledge testing. Assessment plays a crucial role in gauging students' understanding and progress, especially at the primary level. The article discusses various assessment strategies tailored to primary level learners, including formative assessments, performance tasks, and peer evaluations. By implementing effective knowledge testing strategies, educators can provide valuable feedback to students and support their academic development.

Key words: Assessing, educational process, diagnosing, self-esteem, motivation, active cognitive activity, portfolio, self-development.

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Assessing students' knowledge and skills is an important part of the educational process, from the correct setting of which largely depends on the success of training. It is generally accepted that assessment is the so-called "feedback" between teacher and student, that stage of the educational process when the teacher receives information about the effectiveness of teaching the subject. According to this, they distinguish the following goals for assessing students' knowledge and skills: [1]

- diagnosing and correcting students' knowledge and skills;
- taking into account the effectiveness of a separate stage of the learning process;
- determination of final learning outcomes at different levels

In a modern school, the transition from one class to another is based on a system constant control carried out by the class teacher. In many cases, this type of control is supplemented by such forms as tests, tests, organized outside the educational institution regularly and throughout the academic year.

Let's consider several modern methods for assessing educational achievements younger schoolchildren. Among them, the most common method is "portfolio".

A portfolio is a way of recording, accumulating and evaluating individual achievements of students during a certain period of their educational activities. The peculiarity of a portfolio is that it can be used as an external assessment, and as an internal form of introspection, self-esteem and designing an individual trajectory of self-development for the student himself.

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The main purpose of using a portfolio is to teach younger students self-organization of their activities, their motivation for active cognitive activities, the formation of reflexive skills, the ability to carry out adequate self-assessment of one's activities.

Assessment becomes a diagnostic tool that provides feedback to the learner and the teacher about the suitability of the curriculum and instructional materials, the effectiveness of the teaching methods, and the strengths and weaknesses of the students. Furthermore, it helps demonstrate to young learners that they are making progress in their linguistic development, which can boost motivation. This encourages students to do more and the teacher to work on refining the process of learning rather than its product.

"Young learners are notoriously poor test taker... [T]he younger the child being evaluated, assessed, or tested, the more errors are made...[and] the greater the risk of assigning false labels to them" (Katz 1997:1). Traditional classroom testing procedures can cause children a great deal of anxiety that affects their language learning as well as their self-image (Smith 1996).

Babansky Yu.K. notes that teaching methods are ways of interrelated activity of teachers and students aimed at solving a set of tasks of the educational process. The difference between these definitions of the teaching method is that if in the first of them the method is associated with the achievement of the learning goal, then in the second the goals of the method are understood more broadly — as a set of tasks of the educational process. And they provide for the implementation of functions not only of training, but also of development, as well as education, motivation, organization and control.

The classification of teaching methods proposed by Yu.K. Babansky has become the most widespread in didactics in recent years. It identifies three large groups of methods:

1. Methods of organization and implementation of educational and cognitive activities:

— verbal, visual and practical (aspect of perception and transmission of educational information);

— inductive and deductive (logical aspects);

— reproductive and problem-seeking (aspect of thinking);

— independent work and work under the guidance of a teacher (the aspect of teaching management).

2. Methods of stimulating and motivating educational and cognitive activity:

— interest in learning;

— duty and responsibility in teaching.

3. Methods of control and self-control over the effectiveness of educational and cognitive activity:

— oral, written, laboratory and practical. There are other approaches to classifying teaching methods. By the nature of the students' activities (I. Ya. Lerner and M. N. Skatkin). There are five teaching methods, and in each of the subsequent ones, the degree of activity and independence in the activities of students increases.

In conclusion, effective knowledge testing strategies are fundamental for evaluating essential level learners precisely and supporting their academic development. By utilizing a variety of assessment strategies such as developmental evaluations, execution assignments, and peer assessments, teachers can gain knowledge into students understanding and give targeted feedback. These strategies not as it were offer assistance in assessing students information but too foster a culture of continuous improvement and learning within the essential classroom. Eventually, implementing effective knowledge testing strategies can upgrade the educational experience for essential level learners and contribute to their by and large academic success.

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